

pH Dependence of Solubility of Calcium-Cadmium Hydroxylapatites

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The solubilities of solid solutions of Calcium-Cadmium hydroxylapatites determined in the pH range 5.0 to 8.0 decrease with increase in pH of the dissolving medium. This is due to the dissolved phosphate ions function as proton acceptors and being salts of weak acid undergoes hydrolysis in aqueous media and at a given pH it was found to decrease steadily till about 40 mole % of cadmium hydroxylapatite composition was reached and thereafter an increase in solubility with greater proportions of CdHA in the solid solutions a well known phenomenon observed due to destabilisation of the crystal lattice observed in case of allotropes.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, is the major inorganic constituent of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Cd}^{2+}$ exchange in CaHA is of biological importance as it explains the incorporation of cadmium into the human skeletal system. This exchange process results in the formation of solid solutions of calcium-cadmium hydroxylapatites due to the closeness of ionic radii of Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å) and Cd^{2+} (0.97 Å) according to the following equation.

$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2 + n\text{Cd}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ca}_{10-n}\text{Cd}_n(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2 + n\text{Ca}^{2+}$. While the pH dependence of solubility of CaHA has been thoroughly investigated³, similar studies on CdHA and its solid solutions with CaHA are not available. The present work reports a study of (i) the pH dependence of solubility of calcium and cadmium hydroxylapatite in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) the solubility effect with increase of cadmium content in the solid solutions at fixed pH value.

The details of preparation and identification of CaHA, CdHA and Ca-CdHA in the form of solid solutions were reported earlier⁴. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro-analytical determination of phosphate in the saturated solutions of the sample. Potassium acid phthalate-sodium hydroxide and sodium diethyl barbiturate-hydrochloric acid were

used as buffer combinations of the medium of equilibration. The pH was measured with a line operated Backmann pH metre before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2 g of 200 mesh (B. S. S.) solute was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbondioxide free doubly distilled water taken in an air tight polythene container and was shaken mechanically at a regulated speed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to stimulate biological conditions. At the end of the desired period of equilibration required for the attainment of saturation, which was determined previously through dissolution kinetics, the systems were separately filtered through IG₄ crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁵.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples are given in Table 1 and a graphical representation of the solubility behaviour is shown in Fig. 1. The experimental Wt % errors of the determinations of Ca^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} when present together as in the solid solutions were respectively less than 0.20, 0.45 and 0.00 while the corresponding errors when PO_4^{3-} was present either with Ca^{2+} or Cd^{2+} as in the case of CaHA or CdHA are 0.00. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total of 10 g atoms of calcium, and/or cadmium, the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated and given in Table 1. The

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM AND CADMIUM HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sl. No.	Wt%			Molecular formula	Molecular Volume	g. atomic ratio Ca+Cd P
	Ca	Cd	P			
1	39.8	—	18.52	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.31	1.68
2	34.08	9.45	16.9	$\text{Ca}_{9.1}\text{Cd}_{0.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	330.21	1.67
3	28.42	18.69	16.28	$\text{Ca}_{8.1}\text{Cd}_{1.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	325.41	1.67
4	22.97	27.43	15.23	$\text{Ca}_7\text{Cd}_3(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	321.52	1.67
5	19.41	33.38	14.55	$\text{Ca}_{6.2}\text{Cd}_{3.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	316.73	1.68
6	14.6	41.05	13.63	$\text{Ca}_5\text{Cd}_5(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	317.02	1.67
7	11.81	45.93	13.07	$\text{Ca}_{4.2}\text{Cd}_{5.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	310.97	1.68
8	7.95	51.9	12.33	$\text{Ca}_{4.2}\text{Cd}_{5.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	310.27	1.68
9	5.06	56.71	11.76	$\text{Ca}_3\text{Cd}_7(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	306.85	1.67
10	2.17	61.40	11.37	$\text{Ca}_2\text{Cd}_8(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	306.24	1.67
11	—	64.91	10.78	$\text{Cd}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	303.59	1.68

* For correspondence.

Fig-1. pH dependance Cef solubility of Calcium-Cadmiums Hydroxylapatites

g. atom ratios of $\frac{Ca + Cd}{P}$ in a mole of each sample were calculated from the results of the chemical analysis and was found to be 1.68 (theoretical 1.67). The dissolution of CaHA can be considered to be initiated by the hydrolysis of PO_4^{3-} of the hydroxylapatite lattice which leads to the formation of $Ca_3(PO_4)_2$ and $Ca(OH)_2$ according to the following equations.

Exactly analogous equations can be proposed for the cadmium species. So CaHA and CdHA basically undergo the same mode of dissolution leading to the formation of corresponding tribasic phosphate and hydroxide, the solubility being governed by the solubility product of latter. Thus at a given pH CaHA is more soluble than CdHA (see Fig. 1B) in the decrease in solubility of the samples with increase in pH (Fig. 1B) can be explained on the basis of the common ion effect applied to the solubility products⁶. The samples being salts of weak acid undergo hydrolysis in aqueous media⁷ and the dissolved phosphate can function as a proton acceptor according thereby for the observed pH dependences of the solubility of samples. The solubility at a given pH for the solid solutions should normally

decrease as percentage of CdHA increases, as found upto 40 mole % of CdHA in solid solutions. The solubility is expected to increase where there is sufficient increase in CdHA to appreciably destabilise the crystal lattice—a well known phenomena observed in case of allotropes, less stable allotropes are more soluble. For instance aragonite (orthorombic) is less stable and hence has greater solubility than calcite having a more symmetrical thombohedral crystal lattice. Thus the increase in trend of solubility of solid solutions with higher proportions of CdHA could be explained.

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